

Instruct-ULTRA

Integrating Structural Biology

Instruct-ULTRA

WP5 – Reaching new user communities and industry

Lead Beneficiary: P12 - CIRMMMP

Co-leaders: P2 – UOXF, P10 – CNRS, P13 - UU

Deliverable D5.1 Public list of services offered to industries

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Project Objective

Setting up appropriate service provision tools open to industry and new academic communities.

This deliverable relates to task 5.1 (Improving services for industry and SMEs) and task 5.2 (Engagement with SMEs and Industry).

Executive Summary

We report on the activities carried out to publicise the services offered by Instruct-ERIC centres to Industry. A survey of Instruct Centres was carried out to establish their level of involvement in providing access to users from industry. From this a list of Centres and the service that they are able to offer on fee for service was compiled. Web pages specifically for industry have been developed on the new Instruct-ERIC website on which these services are attractively presented and how to access them.

1. Introduction

The Instruct-ERIC offer to industry needs to be clearly defined and procedures in place to ensure that delivery meets industry expectations. Although Industry makes up a potentially large user group for Instruct-ERIC, it is by nature conservative and presenting user cases of successfully delivering services to users from Industry will be critical to increasing Instruct's industry user base. As a first step, a public list of services offered to Industry by Instruct-ERIC has been compiled based on feedback from Instruct-ERIC Centres who have an established track record of working with users from industry. This was based on the results of a survey of all Instruct-ERIC Centres as outlined in section 2.

2. Survey of industry engagement by Instruct-ERIC Centres (December 2017)

All Instruct-ERIC Centres were asked to complete a survey about their involvement with Industry. Results from the survey showed that all Centres have experience with the provision of access to industrial users. Companies were most often large enterprises, using a fee-for-service model in many different sectors (biotech, pharma, chemistry, biomaterials, agri-food and instrumentation). Centres offered a wide range of tools to manage industry access, most commonly Service Level Agreements (SLA) and Templates for Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDA). Most of the Centres are interested to enlarge the services provided.

Services used by industry clients included: Cryo EM, X-ray crystallography, Synchrotron services, Advanced mass spectrometry, Protein production, NMR, EPR, Analytical Ultracentrifugation, Surface plasmon resonance, DSC crystallography. The same survey collected also information on which tools were available at each centre to manage industry services, for example protocols, price lists, standard operating procedures (SOPs) and Laboratory Information Management Systems (LIMs).

Details of the survey questions and an analysis of the results are given in Appendices 1-3.

3. Recommendations from the Industry roundtable (8th March, 2018).

To help better define the needs of industry a round table meeting was convened at the Instruct-ULTRA annual meeting in March 2018. In addition to members of Instruct Centres that provide access to industry three external participants were invited to the meeting representing different perspectives on industry users. The participants were:-

- Maria Flocco (SAB member, Astra Zeneca)
- John Harris (Oxford Biosciences Network)
- Lucia Banci, Roberta Pierattelli, Francesca Morelli (Instruct centre CERM/CIRMMMP, Italy)
- Ray Owens (Instruct Hub and Instruct-UK, Harwell & Oxford)
- Els Pardon (Instruct centre Nanobodies for Instruct, Belgium)
- Darren Hart (Instruct centre France 2)
- José Antonio Marquez (EMBL, France)

Some useful recommendations emerged from the round table discussion as follows:-

- Increase communication by preparing an information package and participate in relevant events.
- Clearly describe the uniqueness of Instruct and what can offer
- Make clear that it can act as a single “solution provider” for structural biology problems.
- Be organized to provide services with a time fame and organization attractive for industry.
- Develop a Training plan for industrial researchers
- Set up a group of a few industrial testimonials for success stories
- Consider the role of a Business Development Manager, as a central point of contract for Industry enquiries

One the key points highlighted by the meeting was the requirement for a simple, single entry point to the different services and technologies offered by Instruct-ERIC to industry. As a first step to address this, a single contact point for industry reachable from the Instruct-ERIC web-page allow industrial users to address messages and queries to industry@instruct-eric.eu. These messages are received by the staff at the Instruct Hub and then redirected to the appropriate Instruct centre.

4. List of services offered to Industry by Instruct Centres

Using the survey results and detailed correspondence with Instruct Centres, a list of services offered to industry has been produced, shown in the form of a table. The list will be reviewed periodically with centres to make sure it remains up to date, as centres offer new services in future.

		Instruct -UK	Instruct -FR	Instruct -IT	Instruct -NL	Instruct -CZ	Instruct -ES
Sample Preparation	Protein Production		✓				
	Crystallisation	✓	✓			✓	
Biomolecular Analysis	Mass Spectrometry	✓				✓	
	Molecular Biophysics	✓	✓			✓	
	Cell Imaging		✓				
3D Structural Analysis	Cryo-Electron Microscopy	✓	✓		✓		✓
	X-ray crystallograph y					✓	
	NMR		✓	✓		✓	
	EPR		✓				
	SAXS		✓				

Table 1. Services offered by Instruct Centres to Industry Clients

4. Development of webpages for industry users

The results from activities outlined in 2 and 3 above have been incorporated into new webpages on the Instruct-ERIC website dedicated to users from industry. A prominent area on the Instruct-ERIC homepage has been devoted to Industry (Fig. 1), with a button that leads directly into information for Industry (Fig. 2).

It was decided that the best way to display the public list of services would be to display services on an attractive webpage “Services available to Industry” (Fig. 3), which is linked to from the main Industry page.

Further content will be developed as appropriate, for example additional testimonials from industry users.

Instruct-ERIC provides open access
to high-end structural biology
services and techniques

Researchers in Life Sciences

Find services and equipment
available in your area and submit a
request to book them.

READ MORE >

Industry

Find out how Instruct-ERIC can
help you learn new techniques
and collaborate with others.

READ MORE >

Access Catalogue

Browse our list of technologies
and services offered by leading
European research centres.

READ MORE >

What is Instruct-ERIC?

Instruct-ERIC is a pan-European research infrastructure in structural biology, making high-end technologies and methods available to all European researchers.

Structural Biology is one of the key frameworks on which we interpret molecular and cellular functions. The main experimental technologies are complementary, and increasingly link detailed atomic structure with cellular context.

Structural Biology is currently in the middle of a revolution enabled by significant advances in the tools (direct electron detectors in EM, advances in synchrotron sources and detectors, XFELs, ultra-high field NMR, super-resolution cryo-light microscopy).

Researchers from Instruct [member countries](#) can [request access](#) to the [service/technologies](#) offered through the [Instruct-ERIC Centres](#).

Fig. 1. Instruct-ERIC homepage www.instruct-eric.eu

Information for Industry

Instruct-ERIC provides a industry with a single point of entry to a wide range of state-of-the-art structural biology techniques and expertise. Through Instruct you can gain access to cutting-edge techniques and technologies along with fostering collaborations with experts in their field. Establishing these collaborations can save huge costs of training and investment in instrumentation that could be accessed through Instruct.

In the last three years, Instruct centres have hosted access visits from over 50 industry partners, representing companies from the Biotech, Pharma, Health, Chemistry, Biomaterials and Agrifood sectors. This includes university spin-off companies, small medium sized enterprises (SMEs) and large companies.

Services include cryo-EM, X-ray crystallography, NMR, protein production, EPR, analytical ultracentrifugation, surface plasmon resonance, DSC crystallography and small angle X-ray scattering.

Tailored to Industry clients

- ✓ World class scientific expertise
- ✓ Single point of access
- ✓ Fast turnaround
- ✓ Flexible service
- ✓ Competitive price for high-end technology
- ✓ IP, NDA and Service Level Agreements available

Gain access to resources and start collaborating today!

[REGISTER](#)

[REQUEST ACCESS](#)

Information for:

Researchers in Structural Biology

Researchers in Life Sciences

Industry

Instruct-ERIC services for Industry

Sample Preparation

Protein Production

Protein Production is available to industry at Instruct-FR1. For information about Protein Production facilities at Instruct-FR1, click [here](#). To request pricing and booking details, use our [contact form](#).

Gain access to resources and start collaborating today!

[REGISTER](#)

Fig. 3. First section of Instruct-ERIC Services to Industry webpage.
www.instruct-eric.eu/industry

years?

3. Please select type of companies engaged: Spin-offs, SMEs, Large Enterprises
4. Please select type of engagement: Fee-for service, collaboration, consultancy
5. Please select the main sectors: Biotech, pharma, health, other

6. If your centre doesn't work with companies, would you be interested to offer services to industry?
7. What service/technology at your centre is/would be available to commercial users:
8. Which of the following are in place at your centre for managing industry activity:
 - a. Templates for non-disclosure agreements
 - b. Service level agreements covering confidentiality, liability, intellectual property
 - c. Price list / pricing policy
 - d. Standard operating procedures
 - e. Laboratory information management systems
 - f. Secure way of holding commercially sensitive data

Appendix 2: Results from Instruct-ERIC Industry Survey 2018

All Instruct-ERIC Centres have interactions with industry on a bilateral basis involving a mixture of collaboration, fee-for-service and consultancy. Survey results of activity over the last three years are summarized in Figure 1. In total Instruct Centres have worked with **66** companies across different industry sectors, including major pharmaceutical, biotechnology companies and instrument manufacturers. Large-scale facilities such as the NMR Centre at CERM and Diamond Light Source are particularly active providing access to instrumentation not typically available to industrial users in-house.

Figure 4. Summary of Industrial Engagement by Instruct Centres (2014-2107) (a) Number of companies (b) Type of companies (c) Type of engagement (d) Sectors of industry (n=7).